

Inverse design of shape-morphing structures based on functionally graded composites

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2D flat shape

3D morphed shape

Forward design
→

←
Inverse design

Outline

1. Motivation

2. Methods

3. Results

Morphing structures

JWST's sunshield

NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center

Aircraft wing

Sofla, A.Y.N., et al. *Materials & Design*, 2010.

Soft robots

Advanced Robotics at Queen Mary

- ❑ Morphing structures have the ability to change their shape as **deployable structures**, improve **aerodynamic** performance, or achieve specific **manipulation/motion**.

Some candidate morphing structures:

Shape-morphing structures that transform from **flat 2D sheets** to **3D shapes** are desired due to simplicity in fabrication and transportation (via stacking).

2D flat fabric

$$\kappa = 0$$

Deformation

3D shape after draping

[Gupta et al. 2019]

$$\kappa = 0$$

□ Isometries cannot alter the Gaussian curvature (κ).

Methods to achieve morphing from flat sheet:

Locally expansion or actuation

Pneumatic expansion

Thermal expansion

But induces excessive strain!

Specific cuts

Kirigami

Lee et al., Nat. Com., 2018.

Axisymmetric-type structures can be formed by making repeated cut patterns around a central hub.

Inverse design problem:

Initial 2D pattern

Final 3D shape

- **How to determine a 2D pattern that deforms into a desired 3D shape?**

Outline

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Start from the beam problem:

We can simplify the axisymmetric problem into 1D beam problem:

□ The load from the transverse and out-of-plane direction will introduce beam buckling.

Tapered beam equation

Tapered beam equation relates the shape of an elastic strip (LHS) under mechanical loading to the curvature of a 3D shape (RHS) using non-linear beam theory.

Tapered Elastica equation:

$$\frac{d}{d\xi} \left[\hat{E}(\xi) \cdot \hat{I}(\xi) \cdot \frac{d\theta}{d\xi} \right] = -\hat{H} \frac{d\hat{z}}{d\xi} - \hat{V} \frac{d\hat{x}}{d\xi}$$

$$\hat{I}(\xi) = \frac{\hat{w}(\xi) \cdot \hat{t}(\xi)^3}{12}$$

Control:

- **Moment of inertia (width/thickness)**
- **Local Young's Modulus**

□ **Control the local bending stiffness to achieve a specific morphing shape.**

Previous work: Uniform thickness and tessellation

Without tessellation

Applying horizontal force and assuming uniform thickness.

$$\hat{w}(\xi) = \tilde{H} \frac{(\hat{z}_* - \hat{z})}{\theta_\xi(\xi)}$$

With tessellation

Following tessellation condition.

$$\hat{w}(\xi) = \frac{2L}{w_0} \cdot \hat{x}(\xi) \cdot \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{N}\right)$$

$$\hat{t}(\xi)^3 = \tilde{H} \frac{(\hat{z}_* - \hat{z})}{w(\xi) \cdot \theta_\xi}$$

Cupola of St Thomas church

Target

FEM

Experiment

Without tessellation

With tessellation

[Liu, M. et al. Soft Matter, 2020, 16, 7739-7750]

- ❑ Structures with varying thickness are difficult to store and incompatible with brittle material.

Previous work: Distributed local porosity

Assuming uniform thickness and following the tessellation condition. Level of local porosity, ϕ , enables bending stiffness to be varied.

$$\phi(\xi) = 1 - \tilde{H} \frac{(\hat{z}_* - \hat{z})}{\hat{w}(\xi) \cdot \theta_\xi}$$

□ However, size of porosity may adversely affect load bearing capacity of morphing structures.

Our work: Modulus-graded beam

Assuming non-uniform modulus distribution with uniform thickness and tessellation.

$$\hat{E}(\xi) = \tilde{H} \frac{(\hat{z}_* - \hat{z})}{\hat{w}(\xi) \cdot \theta_\xi}$$

Graded beam equation

Modulus distribution is achieved by varying volume fraction of bi-phase composites. But...

Target

□ How to determine the composition of each material?

AND

□ How to fabricate the graded composite?

Voxelated graded composites

One strategy involves discretising the geometry using voxels.

- The modulus of each slice can be designed to achieve a certain modulus.

Additive Manufacturing of Graded Composites

Additive Manufacturing of Graded Composites

Increase in voxel size

0.25 mm 0.5 mm 1 mm
50% composition

- Two compatible elastomers are used to manufacture graded composite (FLX9070 is soft and FLX9095 is rigid).

Design principle

Design strategy employed to inverse design desired 3D shape.

Outline

1. Motivation


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graph TD; A[1. Motivation] --> B[2. Methodologies]; B --> C[3. Results];
```

2. Methodologies

3. Results

Validation (FEM vs Experiment)

Target: 3D tessellating hemisphere

FEM

Experiment

□ A good agreement between FEM predictions, analytical solution and experiment.

Load-bearing capacity

It is essential to evaluate their load-bearing capacities, before engineering application.

□ Indentation tests to determine the stiffness and the energy absorption capacity.

Load-bearing capacity

3D tessellating hemiellipsoids with varying aspect ratios.

$a/b = 0.5$

$a/b = 1.0$

$a/b = 2.0$

□ Indentation tests to determine the stiffness (K) and the energy absorption capacity (ψ).

More cases:

A nose cone structure

$$\kappa > 0$$

A trumpet structure

$$\kappa < 0$$

A roof structure

Varying κ

A hemisphere formed using three-phase materials

■ Soft ■ Intermediate ■ Rigid

3 materials

Aggregate patterns of materials

- The same morphing structure using of various **aggregate patterns** in either width or thickness direction.
- This is to avoid generating too many **interfaces** if the bonding is not very well.

Why use composites instead of a single material for morphing?

- Composites can be designed to blend the distinct advantages of two different materials.

Sensing and energy storage

[ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 2022, 14, 29, 33871–33880]

Heat management

[Energy Fuels 2022, 36, 8, 4153–4173]

Electromagnetic shielding interface

<https://physicsworld.com/a/cool-graphene-composites-block-em-radiation/>

Multifunction – Hemisphere (Heat transfer)

Before morphing

After morphing

□ Composite material that exhibits intermediate thermal conductivity.

Multifunction – Hemisphere (Electric potential)

□ Composite material that exhibits intermediate electrical conductivity.

Multifunction – Hemisphere

□ The temperature and electrical potential profiles vary with different compositional patterns.

Composite blending

- Composite material that exhibits favourable properties for both electrical and thermal conductivities.

Potential multifunctional applications:

Spherical Radar Radome

Dome Theatre

O2 arena

Nosecone

Heat shield

Conclusion:

- The modulus profile of tapered spokes needed to achieve a desired 3D deformation was inversely designed using the **Tapered Beam equation**.
- We have achieved the graded morphing composites based on **rule of mixtures, discretised voxels** and **additive manufacturing**.
- **Multifunctional morphing composites** blend the distinct advantages of two different materials and combined effective properties in a single structure.

Future work:

- Achieving **self-actuation** by embedding stimuli-responsive material within the print or as an addition to the printed structure.

Thank you for your attention!

References:

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2. Liu, M., Domino, L., Vella, D.* (2020). Tapered elasticæ as a route for axisymmetric morphing structures. **Soft Matter**, 16, 7739–7750.
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Open-source research code:

Gaussian curvature [Gauss, 1827]

- The Gaussian curvature of a surface is invariant under local isometry.

Summary of the overall framework

Voxelated graded composites

Plotting the composite modulus against the volume fraction for longitudinal direction, E_{xx} .

Interestingly, E_{xx} scales with the volume fraction due to affine deformation, whereby a global deformation is translated uniformly to microscale.

Results follow the Voigt (Upper) bound of rule of mixtures.

$$E_{xx}(\xi) = f_r(\xi)E_r + f_s(\xi)E_s$$

Bending deformation is primarily dependent on longitudinal modulus, E_{xx} , so we only need to match the modulus profile in that direction.

Voxelated graded composites

Plotting the composite modulus against the volume fraction for transverse, E_{yy} , and out-of-plane directions, E_{zz} .

Voxels under constant stress undergo non-affine deformation, resulting from a mismatch of strain.

Points are bounded by the Voigt (Upper) and Reuss (Lower) bounds of rule of mixtures.

$$E_{yy} = E_{zz} = \left[\frac{f_r(\xi)}{E_r} + \frac{f_s(\xi)}{E_s} \right]^{-1}$$

Models such as Hashin-Shtrikman could also be used to capture micro-mechanics of bi-phase materials but at heightened complexity.

Forward

Inverse

Multifunctional – Rectangle shapes

	Soft Polymer (PI + 15% Graphite)	Rigid Polymer (PLA + 30% Carbon fibre)
Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	0.3155	2.01
Electrical conductivity (S/m)	1E-7	2.86E-23

Governing equations:
Transient heat transfer:

$$\nabla^2 T + \frac{\dot{q}}{k} = \frac{\rho C_p}{k} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$$

Electrical conductivity:

$$R \equiv \frac{V}{I} = \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{L}{A}$$

Rectangle shape: heat transfer properties

➤ The temperature profiles vary with different compositional patterns.

Rectangle shape: electrical conduction properties

➤ The electrical potential profiles vary with different compositional patterns.

Some candidate morphing structures:

Shape-morphing structures that transform from flat 2D sheets to 3D are desired due to simplicity in fabrication and transportation (via stacking).

$$\kappa = 0$$

Loading

$$\kappa = 0$$

□ Keep the Gaussian curvature will not cause wrinkling.

If you change Gaussian curvature:

2D flat fabric

$$K = 0$$

3D shape after draping

$$K > 0$$

□ Change the Gaussian curvature will cause severe wrinkling!

[Gupta et al. 2019]

Some candidate morphing structures:

Shape-morphing structures that transform from **flat 2D sheets** to **3D shapes** are desired due to simplicity in fabrication and transportation (via stacking).

Gaussian curvature [Gauss, 1827]

$$K = \kappa_1 \kappa_2$$

□ The Gaussian curvature of a surface is invariant under local isometry.